

TENSILE AND COMPRESSION BEHAVIOUR OF SILICON CARBIDE PARTICLES REINFORCED AL7075 ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: Metal matrix composites augmented with micro particles are highly suitable for numerous automotive and marine applications. This work investigates the manufacturing of SiC-reinforced Al7075 alloy composites and evaluates their characteristics. A two-stage reinforcement mixing and stirring process was used to create Al7075-SiC composites. A 2%, 4%, and 6% adjustment was made to the weight percentage of the SiC particle. SEM used to characterise the microstructure. In accordance with ASTM guidelines, the tensile and compressive strengths of the manufactured composites were evaluated. The even distribution of SiC particles within the Al matrix was shown by scanning electron micrographs. SiC particulate-reinforced composites shown superior characteristics relative to the Al7075 alloy.

KEYWORDS: Al7075 Alloy, SiC, Microstructure, Ultimate Strength, Compression Strength

1. INTRODUCTION

Extensive research has been conducted on material matrices, particularly aluminium, copper, and magnesium, from historical to contemporary and future contexts. Aluminium is a principal metal utilised in the fabrication of composites [1-3]. There are two main types of aluminium alloys: wrought and cast. Zinc, silicon, copper, manganese, and magnesium are the main alloying constituents in aluminium alloys. It is common practice to use aluminium alloys as matrices because of their inexpensive cost, good damping capacity, outstanding corrosion resistance, low density, and desirable isotropic mechanical properties [4-8]. Modern techniques have made aluminium and other lightweight replacements to older materials. For enhanced performance in rigid or robust industrial and aerospace applications, a tiny amount of hard reinforcing particles has been included [9, 10]. The

incorporation particulates into the base material has demonstrated improved physical and mechanical properties in composites. Particle composites are extensively utilised in various applications, ranging from everyday use to sophisticated research, due to their high stiffness and low density [11-14]. They are notable for their elevated temperature performance, excellent properties, as well as superior stiffness compared to the base alloy.

Al7075 with zinc and magnesium as main alloying elements is used in this study to make hydraulic parts and various aircraft constructions (sheets, forgings, and extrusions). Equipment for rock climbing, transportation systems, inline skating, bicycles, and transportable apparatuses are among the further uses [15-20]. These are also seen in places that experience a lot of stress when making the product. The beneficial properties of micro SiC, such as its high strength, increased stiffness, and resistance to wear, led to its selection as the

reinforcing phase. Composite failure is affected by the matrix-particle interface strength, which controls the load transfer efficiency, influences reinforcement and de-cohesion susceptibility, and so on [21–23]. The size and volume percentage of the reinforcing particles are the two most important variables in this context. As the volume fraction rises, the number of dislocation barriers increases, making the material stronger. However, the ductility drops because deformation is concentrated in a smaller area of the plastic matrix, making it less able to handle the strain. Conversely, strength enhancement can be attained by reducing particle size, resulting in a higher particle count for the same volume fraction, while simultaneously maintaining ductility, as particles below a threshold size do not fracture. Larger faults and imperfections are statistically more probable due to the increased particle size, which diminishes the strength of composites in comparison to those with smaller particles [24-30].

The study investigates high-strength, low-density composites for structural and transportation applications through the incorporation of SiC particles. The present study employs the stir casting process owing to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and convenience of machine operation. The composite preparation emphasises ceramic particles reinforced by a novel technique for proportional mixtures in increments of two for the MMC. This technology facilitates the homogeneous distribution of reinforcing particulates within the vortex created by

2. MATERIAL USED DETAILS

2.1 Matrix material

The experimental inquiry utilises Al7075 alloy as the matrix material, with its chemical composition detailed in Table 1 below. The wrought aluminium alloy utilised here is Al7075, with zinc as the primary alloying ingredient, complemented by magnesium. The base material Al7075 possesses a density of 2.8 g/cm³ and a melting point of 660 °C.

2.2 Reinforcement material

The properties of the composite are improved by adding a robust reinforcing material to the aluminium matrix. The reinforced micro SiC particulates used in this experiment have a high hardness, great dimensional and phase stability, and can increase creep resistance, fracture toughness, molten Al7075 alloy in metal matrix composites using stir casting.

Table 1- Chemistry of Al7075 alloy

Elements	Wt. Percentage
Si	0.30
Fe	0.45
Cu	1.80
Mn	0.25
Mg	2.30
Zn	6.10
Cr	0.15
Ti	0.10
Al	Bal

and fatigue resistance. The basic alloy has a density lower than SiC, which is 3.10 g/cm³. To ensure proper mixing with the base and avoid agglomeration problems, the strengthening material is added in increments of two during the composite production process [31-33].

2.3 Fabrication procedure

The stir casting process is the most prevalent and generally utilised method for the manufacturing of Al7075-SiC metal matrix due to its ease and simplicity. Mechanical stirring is the primary component of this process, which is also conducive to mass production and offers a cost-effective manufacturing solution. Initially, the reinforcing micro SiC particles were warmed to 300°C in a distinct oven prior to being introduced into the molten Al7075. This technique is conducted to eliminate or mitigate the wettability characteristics of the micro SiC particles and to ensure even distribution according to ASTM standards [34, 35], with a precise measurement of the known weight of Al7075. The Al7075 metal is contained within the graphite crucible, which is subsequently positioned inside the electric furnace. At 750°C, the Al7075 alloy is heated. It takes four hours of heating in the furnace before the metal melts, at which point the temperature reaches 750°C. The absorbed gases from the molten Al7075.

Using the two-stage method, the gas layer surrounding the particle surface can be disrupted and the particles can be separated while the reinforcement material is evenly metal can be removed by adding the degassing tablet Solid Hexa Chloroethane (C₂Cl₆) [36, 37] and stirring the mixture for 4 to 10 minutes. Then, to make sure that the Al7075-SiC castings have a consistent distribution of reinforcement particles, the micro SiC particles are added to the melted metal in pairs so that they don't clump together.

Figure 1: Stir casting set up

distributed within the matrix thanks to stirring in the molten state made possible by the density difference between the matrix and reinforcement matrix. When fortification is added to the molten Al7075 metal, the zirconia-coated stirrer is continuously stirred to ensure that the tiny SiC particles are evenly distributed throughout the molten metal. Maintaining a speed of 300 rpm for 10 minutes is the target. Once the churning is finished, the molten metal is poured into a cast-iron die that has been heated to 300°C to remove any unwanted particles that may have stuck. Allowing the cast iron die to harden, it has dimensions of 125 mm in length and 15 mm in diameter. Coating the surfaces ensures an ideal surface finish. Upon completion of solidification, the cast specimen was extracted for subsequent experimental procedures; specifically, the cast alloy was machined according to ASTM standards for microstructural analysis using a scanning electron microscope. In addition to this, the cast Al7075 composites are subjected to testing to assess their tensile properties. The method utilised is stir casting, as illustrated in Figure 1, for the investigation of Al7075-SiC composites.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural Study

Both the as-cast alloy Al7075 and the composite with 6 wt.% micro SiC reinforced with Al7075 are shown in SEM micrographs in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. The cylindrical specimens' central segment was used to choose the two samples that were subsequently studied. The second

microstructure (figure 2b) shows that the micro-particles serve as nucleation sites, causing the composite grain size to be more compact and refined than the matrix alloy's. This further indicates that the matrix and reinforcement are strongly adherent and that the micro-sized SiC particles are distributed uniformly and homogeneously throughout the composites, without agglomeration or clustering [38–40]. This mostly results from the efficient stirring motion attained during the two-stage addition of the reinforcement. The SiC particles distributed throughout the matrix's grain border impede grain formation and obstruct dislocation migration within the grains during loading.

Figure 2: Showing scanning electron micro photographs of (a) as cast Al7075 alloy (b) Al7075-6 wt. % of SiC composites

3.2 Ultimate Tensile and Yield Strength

The specimens were subjected to tensile tests using a universal testing machine (UTM) in accordance with ASTM standards. For each composition, the average was determined after testing three samples. Both the ultimate and yield strengths are tested. The effects are shown in Figure 3 shows the curve of the ultimate tensile strength of Al 2219 at 2%, 4%, and 6% micro SiC particle weight

percentages, showing how it fluctuates. The graph shows that the ratio relative to the Al7075 cast alloy grows as the weight percentage of micro SiC particles in Al7075 metal increases. Increased ultimate tensile strength is a result of load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement, which is further enhanced by strong interface bonding [41–45]. This quality is a result of the microstructure and characteristics of SiC particles. Figure 3 shows the yield strength, as a percentage of micro SiC particle weight, of Al7075 at 2, 4, and 6 different percentages. Figure 3 illustrates a 41% enhancement in the ultimate tensile strength of Al7075 alloy following the incorporation of 6 wt.% tiny SiC particles.

Figure 3: Ultimate tensile strength of Al7075 alloy and micro SiC composites

Figure 4: Yield strength of Al7075 alloy and micro SiC composites

Figure 4 illustrates the fluctuation in yield strength of Al7075 in relation to the wt.% of micro SiC particles at 2%, 4%, and 6%. The enhancement in yield strength of the alloy from 174 MPa to 243 MPa is attributable to the incorporation of 6 wt.% of SiC particles. This outcome corroborates findings

reported by numerous researchers [46-51]. The aforementioned statement further reinforces the reliance on weight fraction reinforcement.

3.3 Compression Strength

Figure 5 is a graph showing how the compressive strength of Al7075-SiC composites is affected by the micro TiC content. At reinforcement levels of 2%, 4%, and 6%, the graph shows that the compressive strength of Al7075 cast increases as the weight percentage of SiC particles increases. Ceramic SiC particles increase the compressive strength of SiC-reinforced composites by acting as load-bearing components during the test [52-55]. Additionally, the Al7075 alloy's compressive strength is increased by these ceramic particles, which have a high compressive strength and a considerable amount of hardness. Al7075-6 wt. % composites have a compressive strength of 773.9 MPa, compared to 583 MPa for as-cast Al7075 alloy (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Compression strength of Al7075 alloy and micro SiC composite

4. CONCLUSIONS

- Al7075 alloy composites containing 2, 4, and 6 wt. % SiC were effectively produced using a melt stirring technique with two-step additions.
- SEM microphotographs show that the micro SiC particles are evenly distributed throughout the Al7075 matrix, without any clustering or agglomeration, thanks to the two-stage addition method that was used to incorporate them during melt stirring.
- The Al7075 matrix's ultimate tensile strength was improved by adding tiny SiC particles. After adding 6 wt. % tiny SiC particles to Al7075 alloy, the degree of improvement reached was 28.5%.

- Enhancements in yield strength of the Al7075 matrix were achieved with the incorporation of SiC particles. The yield strength of Al7075 alloy rose from 174 MPa to 243 MPa with the incorporation of 6 wt. % SiC particles. The compressive strength of Al7075 alloy rose from 583 MPa to 773.9 MPa following the incorporation of 6 wt. % SiC particles.

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